

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 680395.

Reactor Optimisation by Membrane Enhanced Operation

H2020-SPIRE-2015 - RIA n° 680395

Start Date: 14th September 2015

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Deliverable Report

D8.4.5_WP8_EMH 5th Semi-annual newsletter

Public

Author(s): Mathilde BOUCHER (EMH)

Task No. : 8.1

Deliverable No. : 8.4.5

Issue Date: 26.03.2018

Number of pages: 13

Identifier: D8.4.5_WP8_EMH_5th Semi-annual newsletter

Summary:

This is the fifth of ROMEO's e-newsletters. The e-newsletters are released twice a year. This deliverable explains how the e-newsletters are created, sent and what makes up the mailing list.

The 5th newsletter has been sent to 103 subscribers.

The appendices display the full versions of the editorial, news and interviews introduced in the newsletter.

Document history and validation

When	Who	Type	Comments
15.03.18	Mathilde BOUCHER	Preparation version 1 (V1)	Approval from Gilbert RIOS (EMH)

Author(s):	Mathilde BOUCHER (EMH)	Approved by the Coordinator : Yes Date: 24.03.18
Reviewer(s):	Marc Kristen	

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1. Creating and sending e-newsletters

The e-newsletters are created thanks to the WordPress and MailPoet Content Management System.

The e-newsletters are sent automatically as emails. The software splits the mailing list and doesn't send the e-newsletter to more than 30 persons at a time so that the e-newsletter is not considered as a spam.

The receivers can either view the e-newsletter directly in the message body or open a page in their browser.

2. Subscribers

We have created 3 mailing lists for the different communication purposes that we may have.

- List 1: all the persons working for ROMEO within ROMEO's partners;
- List 2: other people within ROMEO's partners, not working directly on the project but who might be interested in the project
- List 3: other people not part of ROMEO that partners want to inform about the project.

All 9 partners had the opportunity to send names for these three categories, which gathered **103 people** in March 2018.

ROMEO's 4th e-newsletter was sent to all 3 mailing lists on **Monday 26 March 2018**.

3. Newsletter 5

Please click [here](#)¹ to read ROMEO's 5th newsletter online.

Screenprints of the newsletter are displayed on the next pages.

See appendices for all the links to pdf documents that can be opened when browsing the newsletter online.

¹http://www.romeo-h2020.eu/?wysija-page=1&controller=email&action=view&email_id=15&wysijap=subscriptions&user_id=103

Newsletter

CATALYTIC REACTOR METHODOLOGIES
FOR PROCESS INTENSIFICATION

Editorial

Welcome to the fifth newsletter of ROMEIO.

The project team is happy to start its **3rd year of work to implement an efficient platform for the optimal design of new integrated reactors**. We just had a successful 2 days meeting in Waischenfeld, Germany, where partners shared warming moments and fruitful discussions. Technical issues are overcome thanks to the close

collaboration between partners [...]. The model developed for ROMEIO's membrane reactor module is now running and will be used to investigate the effects of various parameters. We keep having good dynamics to win ROMEIO's challenges !

Enjoy your reading
Prof. Robert Franke, Evonik

Read the full editorial [here](#).

7-9 March : Fruitful progress meeting in Germany

Partners from FAU warmly welcomed ROMEIO's workers in Waischenfeld (near Erlangen, Germany) to hold a rich 2 days progress meeting. ROMEIO's

team gathered from Wednesday to Friday to share and discuss the work done in each workpackage. **No doubt that the dynamic collaboration between partners is one of ROMEIO's strength**, on which the project can rely to reach its key scientific and technical objectives! [Read more](#)

ROMEIO spreads as far as Asia!

Jürgen Loipersböck (Bioenergy 2020+ GmbH) took part in the 6th annual international conference on Chemistry, Chemical Engineering and Chemical Process held in Singapore. He presented the new developed part of gas cleaning, which will be used to prepare the gas before ROMEIO's Water-Gas Shift reactor. Several academic and industrial contacts were made, with the goal to intensify the impact of gasification technologies in the Asiatic area. [Read more](#)

Thumbs up for ROMEIO's video

Watch and LIKE the project video, which is part of the EU communication campaign "Showcase your project". Help us to improve energy efficiency of the industry of the future by increasing ROMEIO's visibility!

We need your vote to have a chance to win free travel and accomodation to attend the next Euro Science Open Forum (Toulouse, July 2018).

LIKE the video on YouTube by following [THIS LINK](#).

Stay abreast of ROMEIO's results

Have you seen the new "results" tab created on ROMEIO's website? Go visit and find out more about ROMEIO's achievements so far!

<http://www.romeio-h2020.eu/results/>

Get to know the ROMEIO team members : INTERVIEWS

Jürgen Loipersböck

Jürgen is a junior Researcher at Bioenergy2020+ GmbH in Austria.

"Over the last years I got more and more engaged with the topic of hydrogen production from biomass. Most exciting here is this combination of chemical reactor and membrane separation."

Read the full interview [here](#).

Jan Hoffmann Jørgensen

Jan is Development Engineer at Liqtech in Denmark.

"While first working with catalysts and then with membranes, I always wanted to combine the two disciplines into developing a catalytic membrane reactor. [...] The favorite part of my job is really to create jobs in Denmark by exporting new technical solutions."

Read the full interview [here](#).

Follow the official Twitter account for the ROMEIO project [@romeo123EU](#) and use #ROMEIOH2020 when you tweet a message related to the project !

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 653605.

4. Appendices

4.1 Editorial by Prof. Robert Franke, ROME's coordinator

REACTOR OPTIMISATION BY MEMBRANE ENHANCED OPERATION

Editorial
Fifth Newsletter, **March 2018**

Welcome to the fifth newsletter of ROME.

The project team is happy to start its **3rd year of work to implement an efficient platform for the optimal design of new integrated reactors.** Thanks to detailed understanding of the processes involved from nano to macro-scale, ROME will enable to set up adapted toolboxes by optimizing choice via modelling and simulation. Based on the use of building blocks, we are very much on the right track to facilitate the conception of apparatus for a large set of applications!

We just had a successful 2 days meeting in Waischenfeld, Germany. Partners from FAU warmly welcomed ROME's team in suitable working surroundings, where partners shared warming moments and fruitful discussions.

Technical issues related to the development of new monolithic membranes are overcome thanks to the close collaboration between partners from RWTH Aachen University, DTU, FAU, LiqTech Int., CSIC, Linde, Bioenergy2020+ and Evonik. The immobilization of ionic liquid catalyst systems on membranes optimizes their performance in the selected reactions. The model developed for ROME's membrane reactor module is now running and will be used to investigate the effects of various parameters. Parallel working group meetings enabled more in-depth discussions about the two respective democases (Hydroformylation and Water-Gas Shift reactions) as well as dissemination activities (supported by EMH).

We keep having good dynamics to win ROME's challenges!

As you can read in this 5th issue, we are also really happy to confirm that ROME is of international interest. Special thanks to Jürgen Loipersböck, Junior Researcher at Bioenergy 2020+ GmbH, who represented the project at the CCECP, Singapore.

You can find out more about Jürgen in this 5th issue of ROME's newsletter. You'll also get a glimpse into the daily working life of Jan, Development Engineer at Liqtech International in Denmark.

Please feel free to contact us via [ROME's website](#) should you have any question or comment.

Enjoy your reading,
And don't forget to follow us on twitter! [@romeo123EU](#)

Prof. Robert Franke - Project Coordinator- Evonik

4.2 News about ROMEIO's progress meeting in Waischenfeld

<http://www.romeio-h2020.eu/fruitful-progress-meeting-waischenfeld-germany/>

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Fruitful progress meeting in Waischenfeld, Germany

Mar 2018 0 Comment

Partners from FAU warmly welcomed ROMEIO's workers in Waischenfeld (near Erlangen) to hold a rich 2 days progress meeting.

ROMEIO's team gathered from Wednesday to Friday (7 to 9 March 2018) to present and discuss the work done in each workpackage. In the middle of Frankish Switzerland, [Waischenfeld's research campus](#) offered suitable working surroundings in which partners shared warming moments and fruitful debates.

On Thursday afternoon, parallel working group meetings enabled more in-depth discussions about the two respective democases (HydroFormylation and Water-Gas Shift Reactions) as well as dissemination activities. Reporters from each group summarized the results of discussions in plenary session. The Steering Committee closed the meeting, summing up the main points to keep in mind to go further within ROMEIO. The next review meeting should take place in Brussels, at the beginning of the last quarter of 2018.

The coordination team highlighted the really good collaboration observed with intensive communication between partners. No doubt that it is one of ROMEIO's strength, on which the project can rely to reach its key scientific and technical objectives!

4.3 News about ROMEIO's participation in CCECP

<http://www.romeio-h2020.eu/project-worldwide-importance/>

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A project of worldwide importance!

Mar 2018
0 Comment

Jürgen Loipersböck, junior researcher at [Bioenergy 2020+ GmbH](#), Austria, took part in the CCECP held in Singapore. He presented the new developed part of gas cleaning, which will be used to prepare the gas before ROMEIO's Water-Gas Shift reactor.

The CCECP

The 6th annual international conference on **C**hemistry, **C**hemical **E**ngineering and **C**hemical **P**rocess ([CCECP](#)) fostered collaborative interdisciplinary research in state-of-the-art methodologies and technologies within chemistry. It had been a really good opportunity to showcase ROMEIO and its first results regarding gas preparation to the audience. About fifty Professors, Senior Researchers and PhD students attended the conference. Also some leading industrial managers participated.

ROMEIO's fruitful participation and impacts

The conference was suitable for small group discussions, which were beneficial for all sides. Several academic and industrial contacts were made, with the goal to intensify the impact of gasification technologies, especially biomass based, in the Asiatic area. Facilitated transport and membrane technology focusing on this effect were one major topic, which will help ROMEIO to succeed with its membrane based Water-Gas Shift reactor.

About the related scientific publication

J. Loipersböck, D. Knöbl, M. Luisser, G. Weber, M. Binder, H. Gruber, H. Hofbauer, R. Rauch (2018). **Hydrogen production by steam gasification of biomass – Improving the gas cleaning unit by using a temperature swing adsorption**. CCECP 2018, GSTF Conference Proceedings. *Publication in progress, link will follow.*

Abstract : Hydrogen production from dual fluidized bed (DFB) gasification of biomass has the potential to help to fulfill the aims of the UN and EU to reduce fossil fuel demand. To investigate the production of hydrogen from biomass a research plant producing 3 Nm³ of hydrogen per hour was set up. First results showed the possibility to produce hydrogen from biomass with a purity of more than 99.99 %. However, techno economic analyze showed the need to reduce consumables. Therefore temperature swing adsorption (TSA) was investigated as an alternative to a biodiesel scrubber. First results show the possibility of using a TSA in the process chain. Nevertheless, extensive experiments have to be done to get enough knowledge of the long term stability and possible cost reduction. (<http://chemistry-conf.org/accepted-papers/>)

4.4 Full interview of Jürgen Loipersböck (Bioenergy 2020+)

<http://www.romeo-h2020.eu/partners-interviews/>

European Research & Innovation Project
Reactor Optimisation by Membrane Enhanced Operation

Interview with Jürgen Loipersböck
Junior Researcher
Bioenergy2020+ GmbH, Austria

“Over the last years I got more and more engaged with the topic of hydrogen production from biomass. Most exciting here with ROMEO is this combination of chemical reactor and membrane separation.”

Date of interview : January 2018
Publication : March 2018

Hi, Jürgen ! Can you please tell us a little bit about yourself ?

Directly after school I started at the competence center Bioenergy2020+. As I was always interested in science I began to study beside work at the University of Applied Science Pinkafeld. I graduated there in June 2016 and began to take over projects in Bioenergy2020+. In September 2017 I started my PhD at the technical university in Vienna.

Beside work and studies I'm very enthusiastic in sports. As Taekwondo trainer I like to work with people, aiming to improve their skills. As Austrian I love the mountains and like nearly every sport you can do there. I do hiking, climbing and a little skiing.

What is your favorite work subject ?

I'm not sure what my favorite work is. I love to work in the laboratory where I "produce" new data as well as to travel to conferences where I can present our new investigations. Also the construction and operation of research plants is a very challenging and interesting topic.

I guess I have no favorite work subject. In my opinion the combination of all these things makes this work so nice.

What does your daily job look like?

I start the day with a coffee. I guess this is my only job routine. As research is very challenging, I face new problems every day. Also every day we have to find solutions for these upcoming problems.

How did you get involved in ROMEO?

Over the last years I got more and more engaged with the topic of hydrogen production from biomass. So it was a good option for me to take over Dr. Rauchs work in this sector. Most

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exciting is this combination of chemical reactor and membrane separation.

What is your PhD about? What objectives do you have to reach to contribute to the ROMEIO project?

I work as researcher now for a couple of years. After my master thesis I decided to stay in this field and start doing a PhD thesis. It will focus on hydrogen production from biomass. Special focus will be laid on process improvement by adsorption processes.

A part of my PhD will be the design of the gas cleaning unit for ROMEIO. A better gas cleaning system will make it easier to produce nice results with the ROMEIO reactor.

“ The construction and operation of research plants is a very challenging and interesting topic.”

What are, according to you, the major challenges to be overcome in ROMEIO?

Combining two processes is always challenging. In this case catalysts have to be developed or adapted as well as new membrane separators have to be design. I expect that this project will help to reduce our energy consumption. For some industrial applications major energy and CO₂ reductions can be expected, if we succeed.

Thanks for your time, Jürgen !

BIOENERGY2020's competences cover research and development topics in the field of small scale, as well as medium and large-scale biomass combustion and biomass-based combined heat and power production systems.

The main role of BIOENERGY2020 in ROMEIO is the demonstration of the Water Gas Shift reaction combined with membrane separation under industrial conditions. This demo plant will use CO or CO-containing syngas derived from biomass.

Date of interview : January 2018
Publication : March 2018

ROMEIO in brief

Funded by European Commission (Horizon 2020)

Start date:
14 September 2015

End date:
13 September 2019

Budget:
6 Million €

Contacts:
Evonik - DE

Project Coordinator - Prof. Robert Franke
Scientific Coordinator - Dr. Frank Stenger
Project Manager - Dr. Marc Oliver Kristen

H2020-EU.2.1.5
Project Reference: 680395

4.5 Full interview of Jan Hoffmann (LiqTech International)

<http://www.romeo-h2020.eu/partners-interviews/>

European Research & Innovation Project
Reactor Optimisation by Membrane Enhanced Operation

Interview with
Jan Hoffmann Jørgensen
Development Engineer
at LiqTech International, Denmark

“While working first with catalysts and then with membranes, I always wanted to combine the two disciplines into developing a catalytic membrane reactor.”

Date of interview : February 2018
Publication : March 2018

Hi, Jan! Can you please tell us a little bit about yourself ?

My background is a MSc in chemistry from University of Copenhagen and a PhD in catalysis from Technical University of Denmark. After university I started up the company that later became LiqTech International, together with a CEO and five student workers.

My first task was development of catalysts for diesel particulate filters but now I spend most of my time on developing silicon carbide membranes for water and wastewater treatment.

What is your favorite work subject ?

The favorite part of my job is really to create jobs in Denmark by exporting new technical solutions. Recently, I have taken interest in using our water membranes in gas applications. One example is to use them as hydrogen dispersers for biological upgrading of biogas.

There is no typical day or week for me. I not only have tasks in R&D but often also in supporting sales or production staff.

What excites you in ROME?

While working first with catalysts and then with membranes I always wanted to combine the two disciplines into developing a catalytic membrane reactor. ROME has made this possible together with a team of highly skilled and motivated European professionals.

What are you expecting from the project?

Apart from the benefits from process intensification like lower emissions and energy consumption, I am of course interested in the new business opportunities for our company in the

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chemical industry. We are already doing some testing with petrochemicals and ROMEIO will give us an idea of the potential and the challenges to be overcome within specialty chemicals and other sectors in the industry. Maybe the project can also generate new ideas for future EU applications.

What are, according to you, the major challenges to be overcome in ROMEIO?

Right now I see the major challenge as stable membrane operation, but I might change my view on that. It's a challenge for us to apply a membrane support layer on a convex surface and it could affect the separation layer.

“ The favorite part of my job is really to create jobs in Denmark by exporting new technical solutions.”

Are you participating in other international projects?

I am also involved in a Horizon 2020 project called AQUALity. It is an Innovative Training Network where I will supervise a PhD student. The aim is to remove Contaminants of Emerging Concern from water and wastewater by combining membranes with Advanced Oxidation Processes.

Thanks for your time, Jan, and all the best for your membranes projects!

LiqTech International is specialised in the development, manufacturing and supply of revolutionary silicon carbide ceramic technology for the purification of liquids and gases.

One of LiqTech's tasks in the ROMEIO project is to optimise the tubular membrane structures. This includes the development of structures with different geometry and pore size. Additionally, LiqTech will be highly involved in the design and manufacture of a reactor module that can be used in the demonstration tests.

Date of interview : February 2018
Publication : March 2018

ROMEIO in brief

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